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**An Ultrahigh Performance Zinc-Organic Battery Using Poly(catechol) Cathode in Zn(TFSI)₂
Based Concentrated Aqueous Electrolytes**

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Abstract

Aqueous zinc-metal batteries (AZMBs) are foreseen as attractive solutions for viable, high-performance, and large-scale energy storage applications, but their advancement is greatly hindered by the lack of pertinent aqueous electrolytes and sustainable cathodes. Herein, we demonstrate an ultra-robust Zn-polymer AZMBs using a poly(catechol) redox copolymer (P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄)) as cathode and a novel concentrated Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous solution as stable electrolyte. The Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolyte demonstrates enhanced ion-transport properties and confers relatively better chemical, electrochemical compatibilities with superior cell performance compared to traditional ZnSO₄ solution. The assembled Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) (2.5 mg cm⁻² polymer loading) cell simultaneously delivers high gravimetric capacity (324 mAh g⁻¹) at 1C, with remarkable capacity of 98 mAh g⁻¹ at 450C. This battery also exhibits extremely high cyclability with only 0.00035% capacity fading rate/cycle over 48000 cycles at 30C. Interestingly, the battery can operate at extremely low temperatures (-35 °C) still maintaining good capacity values (178 mAh g⁻¹). Moreover, ~352 Wh kg_{polymer}⁻¹ specific energy is attractive, while the high value of ~72 Wh kg_{polymer}⁻¹ at unprecedented specific power of ~150 kW kg_{polymer}⁻¹ is particularly intriguing. This overall performance is far superior to the state-of-the-art AZMBs, making it a competitive choice for safe and sustainable batteries without compromising electrochemical performance.

1. Introduction

Renewable energy generation coupled with advanced rechargeable batteries, featuring high safety, low-cost, eco-friendliness, and robust electrochemical energy storage performance are highly coveted towards realizing the sustainable energy-based low-carbon society.^[1-3] Although lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) seem like an obvious choice because of technical maturity, market readiness, and validation, their large-scale applications are limited by high cost, safety issues, poor recycling infrastructure, and growing concerns of resource scarcity.^[4,5] Therefore, in the quest of finding alternative sustainable energy storage solutions, systems based on multivalent chemistries, such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , *etc.* should provide ample opportunities owing to their greater abundance, lower costs, superior safety features, in addition to their significantly higher volumetric energy densities.^[6-11] In particular, zinc metal batteries (ZMBs) are highly intriguing because Zn anode shows high specific capacity (820 mAh g⁻¹), high volumetric capacity of 5851 mAh cm⁻³, non-toxicity, non-flammability, cost-effectiveness, large production, and easy processing.^[12-17] Moreover, differently from other multivalent chemistries (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+}) the relatively higher redox potential of Zn (-0.76 V vs standard hydrogen electrode) makes it the only feasible choice as reversible anode for aqueous electrolytes. Certainly, taking advantage of the potentially large voltage window (> 2 V) and high ionic conductivity of aqueous electrolytes, aqueous zinc metal batteries (AZMBs) might present an excellent high energy/power trade-off which is triggering the growing interest of this technology in the last years.^[18,19]

To date, AZMBs are mainly based on inorganic intercalation/conversion cathode materials such as metal oxides (manganese, vanadium, *etc.*), transition metal dichalcogenides, polyanionic olivine-based phosphates, and Prussian blue analogues.^[12,13,18,19] However, these cathode materials resulted in poor cell performances, exhibiting slow kinetics, low round-trip efficiency, and unstable cycling. This is due to the large cation size which hinders interfacial charge transfer and provokes strong electrostatic interactions between the highly charged Zn^{2+} and the host inorganic framework

causing destabilization of the crystal lattice and significant volume changes upon intercalation/deintercalation.^[6–11] It is also important to highlight that most of these multivalent cathodes still involve toxic and/or environmentally unfriendly elements (except widely used MnO_2), which make further steps critical towards accomplishment of large-scale, sustainable energy storage systems. Therefore, the main challenge of AZMBs is the discovery of advanced sustainable cathodes that are capable of delivering concurrent ultralong cycling stability, high energy, and large power-density.

In this respect, redox-active polymers (RAPs), one of the most versatile organic-based electrode materials (OEMs) have been considered as a metal-free, low-toxicity, and sustainable alternative to conventional inorganic electrode materials.^[20–26] Moreover, their polymeric nature brings about countless possibilities for chemical modifications of the polymeric backbone and the side chains in order to tune the specific capacity, redox potentials, and kinetics, *etc.* Interestingly, RAPs have intrinsic characteristics such as the presence of “large voids” and “soft” structures, then make them especially appealing for the multivalent battery era, providing solid-state transport pathways for large multivalent cations with negligible volume changes upon cation insertion/removal.^[27,28]

Although a plethora of RAPs have been successfully applied as OEMs in numerous rechargeable battery technologies, only a handful of n-type and p-type redox polymers were evaluated in AZMB (see Table S1 and S2, Supporting Information).^[29,30] The p-type RAP cathodes (anion-(de)insertion materials; e.g., poly(tetrathiafulvalene)) in AZMB generally delivered good cycle performance and rate capability but demonstrated low specific capacities (typically, $< 150 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$) due to the limited active sites and large molecular weight of the repeating units. On the contrary, the n-type RAPs (cation-(de)insertion materials; e.g., poly(quinone)) were typically limited by poor dynamic performance and cyclability, yet demonstrated high specific capacities ($126\text{--}372 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$). From these limited examples, it is clear that the development of RAP-based AZMBs is still in its

initial stage, but highly encouraging from the viewpoint of their expected electrochemical performance. However, before realizing a step closer to the anticipated target of ultrahigh performance energy storage-incorporating safety and sustainability aspects into it, further improvement in simultaneous life span, energy- and power-density is essential.

In our previous work, we have demonstrated the universality of bioinspired RAPs bearing catechol pendants to reversibly coordinate/uncoordinate numerous cations including H^+ and Li^+ to Zn^{2+} and Al^{3+} with fast kinetics and ultrastable electrochemical performance.^[31,32] Catechols that produce *ortho*-quinones upon electrochemical oxidation were chosen as the bioinspired redox centers due to the higher discharge potential and enhanced reaction reversibility compared to their *para*-counterparts.^[33,34] Additionally, catechols were anticipated as an ideal electrode for multivalent batteries because suitably located catecholates (1,2-positions) able to create a conducive environment for strong, yet reversible, coordination complex formation with multivalent cations.^[34,35]

In this work, we exploit the above-mentioned intrinsic characteristics of poly(catechol) as multivalent organic cathode to construct ultrahigh performance AZMBs. First, we primarily studied the electrochemical properties of Zn anode and poly(catechol) cathode in two different aqueous electrolytes containing 4 m $ZnSO_4$ and $Zn(TFSI)_2$ salts. It was demonstrated that the newly developed 4 m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ extended the lifetime of Zn foil minimizing the omnipresent parasitic reactions and contributed to improve the kinetics of both the electrodes. Consequently, the Zn||poly(catechol) full-cell in $Zn(TFSI)_2$ aqueous electrolyte not only demonstrated high capacity, superior rate capability and excellent cyclability but also endowed slow self-discharge and low-temperature performances compared to in $ZnSO_4$. Notably, this overall electrochemical performance in the optimized 4 m $Zn(TFSI)_2$ is far superior than the state-of-the-art organic cathodes, and also rival most of the reported inorganic compounds for AZMBs.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ Aqueous Electrolyte Formulations, their Physico-chemical and Ion-transport Properties

The proper selection of the zinc salt dissolved in an aqueous electrolyte is very crucial, as it is in large part responsible for determining the Zn plating/stripping efficiency, voltage window, rate capability, and life-span of the AZMB. In 2016, Zhang and co-workers developed an improved Zn||Mn₂O₄ AZMB utilizing zinc salt having bulky counteranion (namely, trifluoromethanesulfonate, abbreviated as OTf⁻) that exhibited superior electrochemical and transport properties compared to the extensively employed SO₄²⁻-based electrolyte.^[36] Lately, this Zn(OTf)₂-H₂O system has become the standard aqueous electrolyte for AZMB. However, novel anions such as bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (FSI⁻) and di[bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide] (TFSI⁻), greatly investigated in Li-ion batteries, have not been widely explored in AZMB. To the best of our knowledge, Zn(TFSI)₂ was used only in a limited number of works^[37-45] where, in most cases, it was applied in combination with supplementary electrolyte salts,^[37-40,43] and detailed properties of Zn(TFSI)₂-H₂O electrolyte were not investigated in detail.^[41,42,44,45] In this study, we compared the reversibility and stability of Zn in mildly acidic 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolyte (pH = ~3.5) with the conventional ZnSO₄ (pH = ~3.6). The selection of 4 m concentrated aqueous electrolytes is based on previous reports that revealed enhanced stability and reversibility of Zn in near-saturated electrolyte solutions.^[36,46-48] As shown in Figure S1 (Supporting Information), both the electrolyte solutions are homogenous and transparent liquids even after standing for months at ambient temperature.

On the quest of finding better ion-transport properties, 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ possess a relatively low viscosity (5.9 vs 6.4 mPa.s, Figure S2, Supporting Information) at 25 °C, high ionic conductivity (90 vs 60 mS cm⁻¹, Figure S3, Supporting Information), and a higher Zn²⁺ transference number of 0.69 vs 0.55 (Figure S4, Supporting Information) for ZnSO₄.

2.2. Chemical Compatibility of Zn Anode

The effect of the electrolyte on the Zn corrosion was first analyzed by linear polarization experiments (Figure S5, Supporting Information). The corrosion potential (obtained by Tafel analysis) of the Zn in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ increased from -2.4 for ZnSO₄ to +4.2 mV (vs Zn/Zn²⁺). Additionally, a lower corrosion current of 2.2 vs 3.7 mA cm⁻² for ZnSO₄ was observed in the Zn(TFSI)₂. A more positive corrosion potential and lower corrosion current for Zn in Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to that in ZnSO₄ probably suggest less tendency of corrosion reactions and lower corrosion rate, respectively, in the former case.^[49]

Second, the chemical stability of Zn in these electrolytes was assessed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in Zn||Zn symmetric cell configuration at different rest periods (Figure S6a, b, Supporting Information). A concomitant increase of interfacial resistance under open circuit conditions with the resting time was noticed in 4 m ZnSO₄ (Figure S6c, Supporting Information). Wherein contrast, the interfacial resistance was stabilized around 3000 Ω after 24 hours, indicating better chemical stability of Zn in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ against corrosion.

Third, the surface morphology of bare Zn was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) before and after immersion in electrolytes. Unlike basic electrolyte solutions (for instance in 4 m KOH) that are detrimental to Zn in terms of stability and/or reversibility, both 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ were found to be less aggressive towards side reactions on the Zn as observed by less flake formation and open spaces (Figure S7, Supporting Information).

Finally, X-ray diffraction (XRD) was employed to determine the composition of the side products after immersion in these electrolytes. As already well proven systems, the formation of passivation layer of Zn₄SO₄(OH)₆·3H₂O in ZnSO₄ and ZnO in KOH and various by-products (such as Zn(OH)₂, xZnCO₃·yZn(OH)₂·zH₂O and ZnO) was evidenced from XRD pattern (Figure S8,

Supporting Information).^[50] Whereas, XRD of Zn after immersion in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ was almost similar to that of bare Zn without/or minimal formation of such corrosion by-products.

2.3. Effect of Electrolyte in Zn Plating/Stripping Behaviour

Figure 1a shows the Zn plating/stripping reversibility and the electrochemical stability window of the two aqueous zinc-based electrolytes determined by cyclic voltammetry (CV) (left-side) and by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) (right-side), respectively. The CV curves reveal that a facile and highly reversible Zn plating/stripping process was observed in both electrolytes. The corresponding onset potentials of initial Zn plating/stripping were $-0.1/+0.04$ and $-0.06/+0.01$ V (vs Zn/Zn²⁺) in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂, respectively. Notably, a smaller potential separation between plating and stripping and slightly higher current were obtained for Zn(TFSI)₂, suggesting better reversibility and faster kinetics of Zn deposition/dissolution compared to ZnSO₄. Furthermore, LSV experiments (right-side of Figure 1a) reveal that the anodic processes assigned to oxygen evolution during decomposition of water were significantly suppressed up to 2.7 V for Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to 2.45 V for ZnSO₄ (+0.25 V).

Figure 1. Zn plating/stripping tests in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolytes. a) Cyclic voltammograms (first 5 cycles) (left) and linear sweep voltammograms (right) of 4 m ZnSO₄ (bottom) and Zn(TFSI)₂ (top) aqueous electrolytes at 5 mV s⁻¹ in three-electrode configuration with Ti foil, Zn wire, and Zn foil as the working, reference and counter electrodes, respectively. b) Galvanostatic cycling of Zn||Zn symmetrical cells at 0.25 mA cm⁻² and each cycle contains the discharge/charge process for 1 hour, separately. c) Galvanostatic cycling at different areal currents, ranging from 0.25 to 20 mA cm⁻² and each cycle contains the discharge/charge process for 1 hour, separately. Insets enlarge the voltage profiles at various current densities.

We further investigated the reversibility of Zn plating/stripping and stability of Zn using a Zn||Zn symmetric coin cell under galvanostatic condition (± 0.25 mA cm⁻², 1 hour for each charge/discharge cycle). Figure 1b shows that Zn(TFSI)₂ electrolyte shows better reversibility and more stable cycling than ZnSO₄ electrolyte. Average voltage polarization (the sum overpotentials) over a period of 400 hours (200 cycles) was only 45 mV in Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to a higher 80 mV in ZnSO₄ (see insets in Figure S9, Supporting Information). Further extending cycling beyond 400 hours resulted serious voltage fluctuations in ZnSO₄ and cell failure occurred after 600 hours of operation, whereas the cell with Zn(TFSI)₂ steadily sustained up to 770 hours without an internal

short. Moreover, when the cycling tests were conducted at a higher current (5 mA cm^{-2} with the discharge/charge capacity of 1.25 mAh cm^{-2}) once again, Zn||Zn cell with Zn(TFSI)₂ demonstrated the most consistent Zn plating/stripping process (Figure S10, Supporting Information). The Zn||Zn symmetric cells were subjected to EIS analysis while cycling to evaluate Zn-electrolyte interface stability (Figure S11, Supporting Information). The symmetric cells in both the electrolytes seems to exhibit a lowering of interfacial resistance from their initial value upon cycling to a steady value after 50 cycles (Figure S11c, Supporting Information). Notably, Zn||Zn in Zn(TFSI)₂ demonstrated lower interfacial resistance after 25 cycles though it showed an initial higher interfacial resistance ($220 \text{ vs } 175 \text{ } \Omega$) compared to ZnSO₄.

To study the influence of different aqueous electrolytes on the kinetics of Zn plating/stripping, galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) experiments at progressively increasing areal currents of 0.25 to 20 mA cm^{-2} were carried out. It is evident from Figure 1c and S12 (Supporting Information) that voltage polarization remain stable in both electrolyte systems as the current increases from 0.25 to 1 mA cm^{-2} . However, beyond 1 mA cm^{-2} , the voltage polarizations monotonically increased more drastically in the case of ZnSO₄ (Figure S12b, Supporting Information), suggesting superior rate capability for TFSI-based system than the sulfate.

We also assembled Zn||Ti asymmetric coin cells to accurately quantifying the reversibility of Zn plating/stripping by means of Coulombic efficiency (CE) parameter. The CE was firstly determined using common approaches and then according to the protocol suggested for lithium metal.^[51] According to the first method, CE was calculated from the ratio of Zn stripped from Ti substrate to that plated during the same cycle. The CE at 1 mA cm^{-2} with an areal capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} gradually increased and reached $> 95\%$ after 15 cycles (Figure S13a, c, Supporting Information). Remarkably in Zn(TFSI)₂, cell showed a stable and higher average CEs 99% , maintained for 280 hours, implying that essentially almost all the Zn deposited on Ti could be recovered during the subsequent stripping process. Wherein contrast, moderate average CEs of 97%

were noted in ZnSO₄. Additionally, when Zn was deeply cycled to a capacity of 4 mAh cm⁻² at 1 mA cm⁻², once again an improved average CEs of 98 vs 93% observed in Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to ZnSO₄ (Figure S13b, d, Supporting Information). This asymmetric cell continues to operate beyond 280 hours in Zn(TFSI)₂, but cell failure was noticed after 250 hours in ZnSO₄. Furthermore, we tested asymmetrical cells at variable areal capacities in the range of 0.5 to 8 mAh cm⁻² at a fixed 1 mA cm⁻² current density (Figure S14, Supporting Information) and also at numerous current densities (1–15 mA cm⁻²) and at a fixed 4 mAh cm⁻² areal capacity (Figure S15, Supporting Information), which revealed similar improved CEs in Zn(TFSI)₂ compared to the ZnSO₄ system.

According to the second method, a smaller capacity of 0.40 mAh cm⁻² of Zn (Q_c) was repeatedly stripped/plated for 20 cycles from the initially plated 4.0 mAh cm⁻² of Zn (Q_T), leaving a residual Zn of 3.5 and 3.7 mAh cm⁻² (Q_s) for ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ systems, respectively, in the last deep strip to the cut-off voltage (Figure S16, Supporting Information). Once again, the average CE calculated based on the following equation:

$$CE_{avg} = \frac{20 \times Q_c + Q_s}{20 \times Q_c + Q_T}$$

was found to be slightly higher in Zn(TFSI)₂ (97.5%) based electrolyte than in the ZnSO₄ (95.8%).

2.4. Zn Plating/Stripping Morphology

The Zn surface morphology was investigated by SEM after 50 cycles at 1 mA cm⁻² with the discharge/charge capacity of 1 mAh cm⁻² both in Zn||Zn and Zn||Cu cells. The tanglesome deposits of Zn on Zn (Figure S17, Supporting Information) and on Cu (Figure S18, Supporting Information) with mossy structures, dead Zn and uncontrolled dendritic Zn growth appeared in both the electrolytes. Unlike other strategies applied to minimize the dendrite formation such as Zn metal protective coating, water-in-salt electrolytes, electrolyte additives, etc. it is not possible to completely suppress their formation with our electrolyte formulations. Interestingly, when the stripped Zn

surfaces were analyzed a more uniform stripping was observed in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ (Figure S19, Supporting Information), whereas, non-uniformity of stripping with big holes can be easily seen in the case of ZnSO_4 (Figure S20, Supporting Information). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping revealed characteristic Zn, O, S, and C on the cycled Zn anode in ZnSO_4 , probably on account of aforementioned passivation layer by-products (Figure S21, Supporting Information). On the other hand, Zn, O, F, C, S, and N were found on the cycled Zn anode in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ (Figure S22, Supporting Information). Formation of solid-electrolyte interface (SEI) on the Zn that is rich with F, S, and N was also reported recently with electrolyte systems containing bulky organic anions such as OTf^- , TFSI^- , etc.^[37,52,53] However, further analyses are definitely needed to study the formation, stability and composition of SEI more in detail. The XRD was then applied to the cycled Zn anode to analyze the nature of by-products (Figure S23, Supporting Information). The peak intensity corresponding to the Zn hydroxides and zincates by-products in the range of $2\theta = 10\text{--}20^\circ$,^[49,50] was found to be relatively high in ZnSO_4 compared to that in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, once again suggesting better chemical and/or electrochemical compatibility of Zn metal anode in the latter electrolyte.

2.5. Solvation Chemistry of the Electrolytes

The observed differences in Zn plating/stripping behavior from the two electrolytes could be attributed to the association of Zn^{2+} cations with the different counteranions: singly charged and bulky TFSI^- anions (vs SO_4^{2-} with double charge) and the concurrent solvation effects.^[36–38,42,48] In order to corroborate that, we firstly explored the interaction between the water molecules and the different salts by using Raman spectroscopy (**Figure 2a**). A broad Raman band that observed in 2900–3700 cm^{-1} range consisting of several components of the OH–H stretching vibration for a typical strongly hydrogen-bonded pure liquid water was considerably narrowed $\text{ZnSO}_4 < \text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ order, signifying the stronger interaction of the water molecules with the TFSI^- than with the SO_4^{2-} anion.^[46] Noteworthy, a peak on the higher wavenumber side ($\sim 3545 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) appeared in 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ attributed to the water molecules coordinated with Zn^{2+} cations with no or weak hydrogen bonds.

This peak at $\sim 3545\text{ cm}^{-1}$ became the maximum for 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, while the original shoulder at $\sim 3230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and maximum peak at $\sim 3421\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for liquid water were still well maintained in 4 m ZnSO_4 , which then became shoulders in the $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ electrolyte. This suggests that more water molecules are coordinated to Zn^{2+} cation in 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ than in ZnSO_4 , thereby diminishing “free” water molecules population, and potentially disrupt the strong hydrogen bonds.^[54]

Figure 2. Physico-chemical properties of 4 m ZnSO_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ aqueous electrolytes. Vertically offset Raman spectra (a), ^1H NMR spectra (b), and differential scanning calorimetry thermograms (c). Snapshots of 4 m ZnSO_4 (d) and $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ (e) electrolytes during DFT-MD simulations. A representative snapshot from the MD trajectory is also presented for the coordination environment of the cations and anions in both the systems. Colour scheme used: Red = Oxygen, Grey = Zinc, Yellow = Sulphur, White = Hydrogen, Blue = Nitrogen, Purple = Fluorine. (f) The radial distribution function and coordination number plots, and coordination numbers of Zn-H₂O, Zn-anion and anion-H₂O computed from the MD simulations (g). (h) The average number of H-bonds between water molecules in the 4 m ZnSO_4 , $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and bulk water.

Secondly, ^1H NMR was assessed to probe the ion environments in 4 m ZnSO_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ aqueous solutions. Compared to the pure water, ^1H NMR signal of water moved to relatively lower chemical shift (high field) with greater peak broadening in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ than in ZnSO_4 (Figure 2b). This indicates that enhancement of electron density around the H atom (higher shielding effect), probably caused by the reduction of hydrogen-bonds on account of the strongest interaction between salt and water molecules in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ than in ZnSO_4 .^[55] Thirdly, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) showed a sharp endothermic peak ascribed to the melting event occurring at a more negative temperature, i.e., $-38\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ than for ZnSO_4 ($-8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (Figure 2c). Moreover, the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) of $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ was also significantly lower (2.6 J g^{-1}) than the ZnSO_4 (6.2 J g^{-1}) and the pure water (11.7 J g^{-1}). These observations once again attest that significant reduction in hydrogen bonding between water molecules occurred in TFSI-based solution compared to the sulfate.^[56]

Finally, by applying molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, we investigated the microscopic structure of these aqueous electrolytes (see Figure 2d, e for the snapshots and Supporting Information for the Computational Methodology). We are mainly interested in the hydrogen-bonding pattern between the water molecules and also the coordination environment of the cations and anions in both solutions. By analyzing the pair radial distribution function (RDF) of the Zn^{2+} cations, it was determined that the coordination number of Zn^{2+} cation is 6 in both electrolytes (Figure 2f). However, each Zn^{2+} cation is surrounded by 4.8 water molecules and 1.2 sulfate anion in 4 m ZnSO_4 , whereas, it is surrounded by 6 water molecules in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$. Further analysis was carried out by calculating the average number of hydrogen-bonds (ANHB) between water molecules and between water molecules and anions. Indeed, each sulfate anion is coordinated by 12.1 water molecules (each oxygen atom forms hydrogen-bonds with ~ 3 water molecules) in ZnSO_4 ,^[57] whereas in the $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, each TFSI^- anion forms hydrogen-bonds with 6.3 ($2\text{ TFSI}^- = 12.6$) water molecules (Figure 2g). After summing all contributions from each individual salt component, an average value of 18.6 and 13.9 coordinated water molecules is estimated with the 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ and ZnSO_4

respectively. Also, hydrogen-bonding analyses showed that each water molecule forms an average of 2.1, 1.5 and 1.1 hydrogen-bonds with itself in bulk water, ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂, respectively (Figure 2h). Therefore, computational calculations indicate that there are less “free” water molecules in Zn(TFSI)₂ than in the ZnSO₄ solution which is in good agreement with Raman, ¹H NMR and DSC measurements.

In summary, benefiting from the smaller charge density and weaker solvation effect of the bulky TFSI⁻ anion that simultaneously minimize water-induced side reactions and facilitate Zn²⁺ ions transportation and charge transfer.^[36,58] Consequently, Zn(TFSI)₂ electrolyte not only featured superior ion transport properties, enhanced anodic stability, better chemical and electrochemical Zn compatibility, higher stability of Zn plating/stripping and faster kinetics, but also enabled superior Coulombic efficiencies as compared with sulfate electrolyte.

2.6. Electrochemistry of Poly(catechol) Cathode in Zn²⁺-based Electrolytes

The electrochemistry of catechol containing copolymer, P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) (see **Figures 3a** and **b** for representative and exact chemical structure of the polymer, respectively), in Zn²⁺-based aqueous electrolytes was investigated by CV. As shown in Figure 3a, the catechols (QH₂) are irreversibly oxidized to *ortho*-quinones (Q) in the first anodic scan at 1.5 V (vs Zn/Zn²⁺), and the reverse cathodic sweep involves the reduction of Q to catecholates with concomitant Zn²⁺ coordination (Q²⁻(Zn²⁺)) to give n-doped states in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂. In the subsequent cycles, the CV profiles are well repeated, featuring a single redox process with the average peak potential located at 1.25 V corresponding to an anodic peak of Q²⁻(Zn²⁺) to Q transformation at 1.3 V and cathodic peak potential of Q to Q²⁻(Zn²⁺) conversion at 1.2 V within a quasi-reversible one-Zn²⁺ and two-electron process.^[59,60] Similar electrochemical performance was obtained in 4 m ZnSO₄ electrolyte. This n-type redox behavior of QH₂ and Q (macro)molecules in Zn²⁺ aqueous electrolytes has been recently proven experimentally; e.g., *ex situ* XPS,^[59,61,62] FTIR,^[59,61] STEM-EDS,^[61] *in situ* ATR-FTIR,^[63] Raman,^[62,63] and UV-vis spectroscopy,^[63] and also validated by theoretical calculations.^[31,62,63]

It is worthy to highlight that this redox potential is one of the highest reported so far for a n-type polymer making it a promising alternative as sustainable cathode for AZMB offering an optimal average working voltage of 1.2 V in the aqueous electrolyte (Figure 3b). This Zn||polymer cell during charge, the poly(catechol) units in the cathode are oxidized releasing electrons into the external circuit and Zn^{2+} cations to the electrolyte. The uncoordinated Zn^{2+} ions pass across the electrolyte and are reduced and plated on the Zn anode surface by gaining electrons from the external circuit. During discharge, the plated Zn is oxidized to form Zn^{2+} ions, which pass across the electrolyte, and are stored by the polymer cathode in the reduced state through the Zn^{2+} coordination reaction.

Figure 3. Design of Zn||poly(catechol) aqueous battery. a) Successive cyclic voltammograms of P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) for the first 10 cycles obtained at 25 mV s⁻¹. b) Cyclic voltammographic schematic representation of 1.2 V AZMB with Zn anode and P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cathode. The CVs were recorded in three-electrode configuration with P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) or Ti foil, Zn wire and Zn foil as the working, reference and counter electrodes, respectively, in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂-H₂O aqueous electrolyte.

The electrochemical kinetic aspects of P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cathode were investigated in both electrolytes by CV at different scan rates. CVs in Zn(TFSI)₂ were characterized by a smaller peak-to-peak voltage separation at a given scan rate (ν) than that in ZnSO₄ (Figure 4a, d), suggesting faster kinetics in the former electrolytes. Quantitatively, apparent reaction rate constant (k^0) (see Laviron formalism in Supporting Information),^[64] was found to be about 2-fold higher in Zn(TFSI)₂ (7.6 s⁻¹)

than that in ZnSO₄ (3.8 s⁻¹) (Figure 4b, e). Moreover, the higher b-values (power-law relationship as: $i_p = av^b$ is discussed in Supporting Information) and also minor change in the b-values upon the transition region indicate that, although a mixed electrochemical reaction kinetic is operative in both electrolytes, the overall response tends to be less-diffusion-limited in Zn(TFSI)₂ than in ZnSO₄ (Figure S24, Supporting Information). Specifically, a higher capacity_{non-diffusion-controlled} contribution of 70% to the total stored charge for P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) in Zn(TFSI)₂ versus 62% in ZnSO₄ justify the superior rate performance in TFSI-based electrolyte (Figure 4c, f) (see detailed discussion in Supporting Information). This kinetic behavior was further substantiated by EIS measurements (see Supporting Information for detailed analysis) which revealed higher apparent Zn²⁺ ion diffusion coefficient (D_{app}) and lower relaxation time constant (τ_0) in Zn(TFSI)₂ (7.6×10^{-8} cm² s⁻¹ and 0.9 s, respectively) than those in ZnSO₄ (4.2×10^{-8} cm² s⁻¹ and 4.5 s, respectively) (Figure S25b, d, Supporting Information).

Figure 4. Comparative electrochemical kinetic evaluation of P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolytes. a, d) Cyclic voltammograms at different scan rates. The CVs are normalized by the peak anodic current to show the peak shift with the scan rates. b, e) Laviron plots: indicating the variation of anodic and cathodic peak positions (Ep), and ΔE_p as a function of the scan rate (in logarithmic scale). c, f) Normalized capacity vs scan rate^{-1/2} plots allow

the quantification of diffusion-controlled and non-diffusion-controlled capacity contributions to the total stored charge. The y -intercept corresponds to the extrapolation of the infinite scan rate capacity (% capacity_{non-diffusion-controlled}) using normalized capacities in the non-diffusion-controlled region.

In summary, the higher non-diffusion-limited capacity contributions (as revealed from power law, normalized capacity vs $v^{-1/2}$ and Bode plot analyses) in Zn(TFSI)₂ on account of faster redox reactions (higher k^0), facilitated Zn²⁺ ion mobility (higher D_{app}) and accelerated relaxation (shorter τ_0) should impart superior dynamic behavior to P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) film in the TFSI-based electrolyte than in the conventional ZnSO₄.

2.7. Comparative Electrochemical Performance of Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) Cells in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂

2.7.1. Rate Capability Assessment

Figure 5a–d show the comparative rate performance of Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) cells in different aqueous electrolytes with the representative specific capacity–voltage profiles depicted in Figure 5a, b. At a low C-rate of 1C, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) in 4 m ZnSO₄ delivered a reversible discharge capacity of 307 mAh g⁻¹ (89% capacity utilization) with an initial Coulombic efficiency of 72%. Interestingly, in Zn(TFSI)₂, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) demonstrated both higher discharge capacities of 324 mAh g⁻¹ (94% capacity utilization) and enhanced Coulombic efficiencies of 92%. The higher Coulombic efficiencies in TFSI-anion containing electrolytes at this slow C-rate could be due to the minimized irreversible charging capacity contribution on account of their enhanced anodic stability (Figure 1).^[36]

Figure 5. Rate performance studies of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cells in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolytes. a, b) Representative specific capacity–voltage profiles at various C-rates in 4 m ZnSO₄ (a), and Zn(TFSI)₂ (b). c) Discharge capacity vs. cycle number. d) Discharge capacity retention at different C-rates. The discharge capacities at higher C-rates are normalized with respect to the discharge capacity at 1C (1C = 344 mA g⁻¹). e) Nyquist plots, and f) Plots showing the correlation between real (Z')-part of complex impedance and $\omega^{-1/2}$ in the semi-infinite diffusion region to calculate the apparent diffusion coefficient in full-cells. EIS data were collected in the 0.01–10⁵ Hz frequency range using a sinusoidal

signal with an amplitude of 10 mV ($V_{\text{rms}} \approx 7.07$ mV) at equilibrium discharge potential of 1.15 V (~50% depth-of-discharge). The thickness of the electrodes used for this study was 82 μm .

With increasing C-rates, both the capacities (Figure 5c) and consequently their capacity retentions (capacities at higher C-rates w.r.t. the capacity at 1C; Figure 5d) decreased monotonically in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2 < \text{ZnSO}_4$ order. For instance, the discharge capacities (and their percent retentions) were 92 (30%) and 148 (45%) mAh g^{-1} at 150C (~47 A g^{-1}) in ZnSO_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, respectively. Even at an extreme C-rate of 1350C (a sub 3 s charge/discharge period), $\text{Zn}||\text{P}(4\text{VC}_{86}\text{-stat-SS}_{14})$ in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ still registered considerable capacities of 65 mAh g^{-1} (20% capacity retention), while in ZnSO_4 , the cell was almost non-functioning. Furthermore, when the C-rate was brought back to 1C, nearly quantitative capacity recovery was observed in both the cases, signifying a strong tolerance to the rapid Zn^{2+} ions coordination/uncoordination reactions. Due the sloping nature of GCD profiles, the average voltage obtained at the slowest C-rate of 1C was calculated to be ~1.1 V, which is slightly lower than that obtained by CV (1.2 V) (Figure S26, Supporting Information). Furthermore, double-layer capacity contribution of CNTs to the total capacity in the composite cathodes (that contain 40 wt% of CNTs) was very minimal, and therefore can be neglected (Figure S27, 28, Supporting Information).

We also characterized the $\text{Zn}||\text{P}(4\text{VC}_{86}\text{-stat-SS}_{14})$ full-cell by EIS, which revealed similar lower charge-transfer resistance (164 versus 209 Ω) and higher D_{app} in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ ($1.37 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) than that in ZnSO_4 ($0.8 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) (Figure 5e, f). Benefiting from the optimization of TFSI-based electrolytes for superior rate performance collectively at the anode (improved Zn plating/stripping) and the cathode (improved poly(catechol) kinetics), $\text{Zn}||\text{P}(4\text{VC}_{86}\text{-stat-SS}_{14})$ full-cells demonstrated improved rate capability in $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2 > \text{ZnSO}_4$ order.

2.7.2. Cycle-Life Assessment

The cycling stability of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cells in different aqueous electrolytes was compared by GCD studies at 10C. Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) attained stable capacities of 242 and 274 mAh g⁻¹ after few initial QH₂-to-Q activation cycles (<3) in ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂, respectively, and impressively retained 71 and 85% of their initial capacities over 12 500 repeated full charge/discharge cycles (**Figure 6a** and Figure S29a, b, Supporting Information). More strikingly, when Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) was cycled in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ at high operational rate of 30C, the cell demonstrated an ultralong life-span; sustaining reversible capacity at 184 mAh g⁻¹ with a remarkable capacity retention of 83% after prolonged 48 000 cycles, losing a minimal 0.00079 mAh g⁻¹ / cycle or 0.418 mAh g⁻¹ / day (total cycling period of 91 days) (Figure S29c, Supporting Information). It is also worth to mention here that after initial few activation cycles, the average Coulombic efficiencies in all of the cycling tests remained more than 99%. Our previous works demonstrated the ultralong cycling stability of poly(catechol)s both in aqueous^[31] and organic electrolytes,^[65,66] and was primarily attributed to their binder nature that greatly suppresses the active-material dissolution into the electrolyte. Moreover, the observed improved cycling stabilities in Zn(TFSI)₂ > ZnSO₄ order is once again ascribed to the enhanced reversibility and higher stability of both the Zn anode and P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cathode in the TFSI-based electrolyte than in the sulfate.

Figure 6. Comparative electrochemical performance of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cells in different aqueous electrolytes. a) Ultralong cyclic performance: discharge capacities and Coulombic efficiencies measured at 10C in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolytes. b) Self-discharge studies: normalized capacity (circles) and Coulombic efficiency (stars). Discharge capacities at different resting times were normalized with respect to the discharge capacity that obtained without rest. c) Low-temperature operativity: Discharge capacity vs cycle number, recorded at different C-rates (from 2C to 30C) and at different temperature (from +25 °C to -35 °C).

2.7.3. Self-Discharge

Self-discharge ability of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) in 4 m ZnSO₄ and Zn(TFSI)₂ was evaluated by interrupting galvanostatic cycling of the cells for different resting periods, i.e., 12, 24, 48, and 96 h (Figure S30a, Supporting Information). Decay in capacity and Coulombic efficiency was observed in both the cases on account of voltage losses, but this decay was slightly aggressive in ZnSO₄ (Figure 6b and Figure S30b, c, Supporting Information). Furthermore, the recoverable capacity after self-discharge experiment was also slightly higher (93 versus 90%) in Zn(TFSI)₂ (Figure S30d, e, Supporting Information). Definitely, good self-discharge performance is an important requisite for the design of practical battery, further improvements in this regard are needed.

2.7.4. Low-Temperature Performance

We further exploited the low melting temperature of 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ (-38 °C versus -8 °C for ZnSO₄, Figure 2c) to evaluate galvanostatic rate performance of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cells at different

temperatures, ranging from +25 to -35 °C. As shown in Figure 6c, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in 4 m ZnSO₄/Zn(TFSI)₂ delivers discharge capacities of 293/325, 264/300, 229/269, 207/245 mAh g⁻¹ and 236/264, 198/241, 155/207, 120/176 mAh g⁻¹ at 2C and 30C, respectively, and at an operational temperatures of +25, +10, 0, and -10 °C, respectively. In fact, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ not only attained higher capacities at all the C-rates, but their retention at lower temperatures (compared to the capacity at +25 °C) were also superior to that in ZnSO₄ (Figure S31–33, Supporting Information). Furthermore, at rather low temperatures of -25 and -35 °C, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ can still maintain high discharge capacities of 213 and 179 mAh g⁻¹, respectively, at 2C, and yet impressively sustain 138 and 101 mAh g⁻¹, respectively, at a high C-rate of 30C, that correspond to 52 and 38% capacity retention compared to the capacity at +25 °C. On the contrary, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in 4 m ZnSO₄ was limited by the decreased operation temperature, delivering insignificant capacities below -10 °C. Additionally, when the operational temperature was reset to +25 °C, after low-temperature rate performance experiments, the capacities of Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) cells in both the electrolytes were almost recovered to their initial values, suggesting negligible intolerance of cell components towards the low-temperature. Moreover, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ was able to cycle satisfactorily at -35 °C, retaining 97.4% of its initial capacity over 44 cycles, with quantitative Coulombic efficiencies (Figure S34, Supporting Information).

2.8. Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) vs State-of-the-art AZMBs

The cell performance of Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat-SS14}) in the optimized 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolyte is compared with the state-of-the-art AZMBs across different classes of cathodes, including small organic molecules, redox-active polymers (RAPs), and inorganic compounds (Table S1–S3, Supporting Information). The average discharge potential of 1.1 V and the maximum attained specific discharged capacity of 324 mAh g⁻¹ (at 1C) are higher than most of the reported RAPs (#s, 10–19 in **Figure 7a**), higher than most of the traditional MnO₂ and polyanionic olivine-based phosphate

compounds, and close to that of vanadium-based compounds (Figure S35, Supporting Information). Despite the high capacity of vanadium-based compounds, they still fall in low specific energy zone owing to their low discharge potentials (typically, 0.6–0.8 V).

Figure 7. Comparing Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cell performances with the state-of-the-art AZMBs, mostly comprising organic cathodes. a) Average discharge potential vs specific capacity. b) Specific discharge energy vs specific discharge power. c) Cycling performances showing % capacity retention against cycle index, and capacity decay rate per cycle (in logarithmic scale) is shown in the inset. d) Specific discharge energy vs specific discharge power at low temperature. The specific energy/power values are based on the mass of polymer in the cathode. All these plots for various active-materials are computed by considering some of the best performing organic cathode materials in their class (see Table S1).

(i) This work (solid stars): P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂.

(ii) Small organic molecules (semi-filled symbols): *p*-chloranil (1),^[67] calix[4]quinone (2),^[63] pyrene-4,5,9,10-tetraone (3),^[61] 1,4 bis(diphenylamino)benzene (4),^[68] triangular phenanthrenequinone-based macrocycle (5),^[69] dibenzo[*b,i*]thianthrene-5,7,12,14-tetraone (6),^[70] 3,4,9,10-perylenetetracarboxylic dianhydride (7),^[71] tetracyanoanthraquinodimethane (8),^[72] and phenazine (9)^[73].

(iii) RAPs (filled symbols): poly(benzoquinonyl sulfide) (10),^[74] poly(dopamine) (11),^[59] poly(catechol) (12),^[62] Cu₃(HHTP)₂ (HHTP = 2,3,6,7,10,11-hexahydroxytriphenylene) (13),^[75] poly(tetrathiafulvalene) (14),^[76] poly(aniline-S) (15)^[77], poly(2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidinyloxy-4-yl vinyl ether) (16),^[78] polyarylimide covalent organic framework (17),^[79] poly(dopamine) (18)^[80], and hydroquinone covalent organic framework (19)^[81].
 (iv) inorganic compounds: monoclinic VO₂ (D) (26),^[82] VO₂ (27),^[83] Na₂V₆O₁₆·3H₂O (31),^[84] NH₄V₄O₁₀ (32),^[85]

The Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) also demonstrated exceptional high rate performance; superior to all of the previously reported AZMBs. This outstanding rate capability is further reflected in specific discharge energy vs specific discharge power plots (Figure 7b). Note that the specific energy/power values are based on the mass of active-material in the cathode, and compared with organic cathodes having similar or even lower mass loading than ours (2.5 mg cm⁻²). Simultaneous high specific capacity, high discharge potential, and ultrafast kinetics in the optimized 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ aqueous electrolyte endowed Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cell with the specific discharge energy as high as ~352 Wh kg⁻¹, where the high value of ~72 Wh kg⁻¹ was still achieved at the unprecedented specific discharge power of ~150 kW kg⁻¹. This steady and high specific energy over a wide range of power values is obviously superior than the reported organic electrodes (Figure 7b). Such an exceptional electrochemical performance highlights the suitability of our system for different energy storage applications, especially where high specific power is required to store or deliver energy in a short time. Further, by taking account of total mass of both electrodes (theoretical anode consumption of Zn and cathode, including CNT additives), the energy density of Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) was calculated to be ~200 Wh kg_{cell}⁻¹, which is definitely an encouraging value for an aqueous battery.

Yet another stimulating merit of our Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cell is its outstanding cycling stability. However, comparing the cyclability (capacity retention per cycle) with the reported systems is not straight forward, which depends on many factors, such as cycling rate, mass loading, depth of charge/discharge, temperature, *etc.* Here we tried to compare our battery with those tested in similar experimental conditions, for instance at 30 C (~10 A g⁻¹). Despite an impressive demonstration of the long-term cyclability of 3,4,9,10-perylenetetracarboxylic dianhydride (7),^[71] poly(aniline-S)

(15)^[77], and VO₂ (27),^[83]-based AZMBs that retained 68, 70, and 79% capacity over 1000, 2000, and 10 000 cycles, respectively, longer cycling was not reported (Figure 7c). Very recently, Yang et al. reported the extended cycling of Zn||monoclinic VO₂ (D) (26) up to 30 000 cycles, but adversely this system was able to retain only 30% of its initial capacity.^[82] Remarkably, our Zn||4 m Zn(TFSI)₂|P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) was subjected to much prolonged cycling test over an extended period of 91 days that comprised 48 000 cycles at 30C, which displayed an outstanding 83% capacity retention. To the best of our knowledge, the 48 000 GCD cycles are currently the longest reported for AZMBs. Moreover, high capacity retention of our system over the extended cycling index, imparted an extremely low capacity decay rate value of 0.00035% per cycle (Figure 7c). Most notably, such a low attenuation rate per cycle is still at least 1.2- and 6.5-fold higher than the second-best cycling, NH₄V₄O₁₀ (32) (but tested only for 1000 cycles),^[85] and VO₂ (D) that tested for 30 000 cycles,^[82] respectively.

We further compared low-temperature operativity of Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) in 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂ with recently reported AZMBs, such as Zn|| δ -MgVO with PVA/ glycerol gel,^[86] Zn||NiCo with sodium polyacrylate hydrogel,^[87] Zn||rGO/MnO₂ with PVA/glycerol gel,^[88] and Zn||PANI with 7.5 m ZnCl₂ aqueous electrolytes.^[89] All these systems (except, Zn|| δ -MgVO) delivered lower discharge capacities than our battery at the tested temperature range from +25 to -35 °C (Figure S36, Supporting Information). Despite Zn|| δ -MgVO was characterized by the higher capacity at -25 °C, which attained at low current density of 0.1 A g⁻¹, our battery simultaneously achieved superior specific discharge energy and power values on account of enhanced rate performance even at -25 and -35 °C, once again outperforming these reported AZMBs (Figure 7d).

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we demonstrated the applicability of redox-active copolymer bearing catechol pendants, P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄)/CNTs as the binder- and metal current collector-free buckypaper

cathode for rechargeable AZMBs. The reversible reduction/oxidation of *ortho*-quinone (generated from catechol)/catecholate redox couple, accompanied by coordination/uncoordination of Zn^{2+} on the cathode side and stripping/plating of Zn at the anode end resulted in an AZMB with an optimal working voltage of 1.1 V. First, the optimized 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ aqueous electrolyte not only demonstrated enhanced ion-transport properties, but also conferred better chemical and electrochemical compatibility towards Zn anode, with improved Zn||Zn and Zn||Ti or Cu cell performance compared to traditional ZnSO_4 solution. Then, the assembled Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) full-cell in 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ exhibited enhanced active-material utilization (94 vs 89%), higher initial Coulombic efficiency (92 vs 72%), superior rate capability (retained 65 mAh g⁻¹ (20%) vs ~2 mAh g⁻¹ (<1%) of their initial capacities (324 vs 307 mAh g⁻¹) at 1350C), better cycling stability (retained 85 vs 71% of their initial capacities after 12 500 cycles at 10C) and low temperature operativity (178 vs 0 mAh g⁻¹ at -35 °C) compared to ZnSO_4 . The improved electrochemical performance in TFSI-based electrolyte is attributed to the reduced solvation effects associated with the Zn^{2+} , stemming from the singly charged and bulky nature of TFSI counteranion (vs SO_4^{2-} with double charge) as revealed by combined ¹H NMR, Raman, DSC and MD simulation analyses, resulting in facile, faster and steadier electrode reactions compared to the traditional ZnSO_4 electrolyte. Furthermore, Zn||P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) in the optimized 4 m $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ -H₂O electrolyte delivered an impressive specific energy of ~352 Wh kg_{polymer}⁻¹, where the high value of ~72 Wh kg_{polymer}⁻¹ was still achieved at the unprecedented specific discharge power of ~150 kW kg_{polymer}⁻¹, together with remarkable cycling stability (capacity retention of 83% over an extended 48 000 cycles at 30C rate with an extremely low capacity fading rate of 0.00035% per cycle). This overall performance in terms of concurrent ultralong cycling stability, high specific energy-, and large power is far superior than the reported Zn-organic batteries. Therefore, the combination of abundant and high-capacity Zn metal anode, the high safety of mild acidic concentrated aqueous electrolyte and presumably economical, environmentally benign, and sustainable poly(catechol) based ultrarobust organic cathode should

hold a great prospect for large-scale energy storage applications without compromising its electrochemical performance.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: Zinc sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\geq 99.5\%$, Sigma-Aldrich), zinc bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide ($\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$, 99.5%, Solvionic), anhydrous 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, $\geq 99.5\%$, Sigma-Aldrich), thin multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNTs; Elicarb® MW, Thomas-Swan) and carbon paper (Toray TP-060, QUINTECH) were used as received. Zinc (Zn, 99.98%, Alfa Aesar) and Titanium (Ti, 99.99%, Alfa Aesar) foils were polished with sand paper to remove surface oxide layer, washed successively with 3% HCl, ethanol and milli-Q water, and dried overnight at 60 °C under vacuum. The synthesis of redox-active copolymer, P(4VC_{86-stat}-SS₁₄) ($M_n \approx 13.0$ kg/mol and $M_w/M_n \approx 1.22$) bearing catechol pendant was described in our previous publication (Supporting Information).^[65]

General Characterization. Thermo Scientific STAR A214 pH meter was employed to test pH values of different Zn-based aqueous solutions. The rheological properties of the liquid electrolytes were investigated using a TA HR20 rheometer at a temperature of 25 °C. The viscosities were determined using a ETC Upper 25.0 mm parallel plate, FOR Peltier plate use Stainless steel, measuring system. The measurements were carried out within a rotation speed range from 1 to 200 s⁻¹. A sample frequency of 8 points per decade and a gap of 1000 μm, were applied. Liquid viscosities were measured by a steady state flow mode. ¹H NMR spectra were recorder with Bruker Avance III/HD 100 MHz spectrometer. Samples for ¹H NMR were prepared by dissolving 4 m ZnSO₄ or Zn(TFSI)₂ in H₂O:D₂O (50:50 wt%). Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature using a JASCO NRS-5100 spectrometer equipped with an exciting Ar laser (532 nm). Electrolyte solutions in the quartz cuvette were directly used for the Raman measurement. Differential scanning calorimetric (DSC)

analysis was performed on TA DSC Q 100 thermal analyzer calibrated with indium, at a heating/cooling rate of $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, under a flowing nitrogen atmosphere. The melting temperature (T_m) and the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) were determined using the TA analysis software provided with the instrument. Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM; Hitachi TM-1000) was employed to observe the morphologies of Zn deposits on the Zn-metal anodes, or the Ti or Cu foils equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrometer for elemental composition analysis. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded in a PANalytical Empyrean diffractometer with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54178\text{ \AA}$) at a scanning rate of $0.2^{\circ}\text{ s}^{-1}$.

Preparation of RAP/CNTs buckypaper electrodes: Without any statement, we fixed the composite electrode composition of RAP:CNTs to 60:40 wt%. This composite cathode is a RAP-supported, self-standing, metal current collector- and binder-free CNTs buckypaper, fabricated by dispersing CNTs in the RAP-dissolved NMP solution, followed by vacuum-assisted filtration processes prepared following our recent articles. The mussel-inspired bioadhesion propensity of poly(catechol) onto the high surface area CNTs *via* their well-known π - π interactions is exploited to fabricate the binder- and current collector-free cathodes.^[65,66] Excluding the utilization of an external binder in the electrode is an added advantage to increase the energy density of the device and prolong its life span by avoiding spurious reactions arising from the binder.^[90] For instance, buckypaper electrode of 2.5 mg cm^{-2} polymer mass loading is fabricated as following: 28.9 mg of CNTs were dispersed in 20 mL 1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) using a tip sonicator, followed by addition of 43.4 mg of RAP, proceeding to sonication for 2 h in a bath sonicator (Branson 2510, 100 W, 42 kHz) and overnight stirring to prepare the electrode ink. The suspension was filtrated through a Nylon filter (pore size $\sim 0.45\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) with the aid of vacuum, followed by thorough rinsing with NMP to remove loosely bound polymer. The buckypaper was carefully peeled off from the filter and dried overnight at $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum. The buckypaper was cut into circular discs with a diameter of 12 mm with an approximate 2.5 mg cm^{-2} areal mass loading of the active-material.

Preparation of coin cells: Zn||Zn, Zn||Ti and Zn||RAP batteries were assembled using a Zn foil, Ti foil or circular disc (12 mm diameter) of RAP/CNTs as the cathode, respectively, Zn foil (10 mm diameter) as the anode and a pair of porous Whatman® glass microfiber filters (Grade GF/B) soaked with ≈ 200 μL of electrolyte in CR2032 coin cells. The aqueous electrolytes were prepared by dissolving ZnSO_4 or $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ in degassed milli-Q water to a 4 m concentration. The cells were assembled in a high-purity argon-filled glovebox (MBraun; $\text{H}_2\text{O} < 0.5$ ppm and $\text{O}_2 < 1.5$ ppm) to avoid any possible contamination by oxygen.

Electrochemical Measurements: Corrosion tests were carried on an electrochemical workstation (Biologic SP-150, Bio-Logic Science Instruments Co.). Linear polarization measurements were conducted in a three electrode configuration, in which the Zn foil (0.25 cm^2), the Zn plate, and the Zn wire were used as the working, the counter electrodes, and the reference electrodes, respectively. The corrosion potential and corrosion current were calculated from Tafel fit system in electrochemical workstation. Ionic conductivities of aqueous electrolytes were tested in SS||SS, in the frequency range of $10^{-1} - 10^6$ Hz by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using a sinusoidal signal using the electrochemical workstation with an amplitude of 10 mV ($V_{rms} \approx 7.07$ mV) at an OCV. Zn^{2+} transference number was evaluated in Zn||Zn symmetrical cell, subjected to a three-step electrochemical protocol consisting of an impedance spectroscopy followed by chronoamperometry and finally an impedance spectroscopy using a Bio-Logic VMP3 potentiostat. Both impedance measurements were carried out with AC amplitude of 10 mV, in the frequency range between 10^6 Hz and 10 mHz at OCV. A constant DC potential of 25 mV was applied in the chronoamperometric step, until steady state was reached. The Zn plating/stripping properties and the electrochemical stability window of different aqueous and organic electrolytes were determined by cyclic voltammograms (CVs) and linear sweep voltammograms (LSVs), respectively, in three-electrode configuration with Ti foil, Zn wire and Zn foil as the working, reference and counter electrodes, respectively. Both these CV and LSV experiments were performed with a Bio-logic VMP3 multichannel

Potentiostat/Galvanostat (Biologic SP-150). The reversibility, cycling, rate performance and Coulombic efficiencies of the aforementioned electrolyte systems were evaluated by galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) experiments with a Neware battery cycler at 25 °C in Zn||Zn symmetrical and Zn||Ti or Zn||Cu asymmetrical coin cells, respectively. The CV profiles of RAPs were obtained using a flooded three-electrode electrochemical cell with RAP/CNTs ink modified glassy carbon (GC, with an area of 0.07 cm²), Zn wire and Zn foil as the working, reference and counter electrodes, respectively, in different Zn²⁺-containing aqueous electrolytes. The electrode ink was uniformly deposited on a masked GC, and dried under vacuum to remove the solvent. The electrolyte was degassed with dry argon, and voltammograms were recorded at room temperature under a positive pressure of argon atmosphere. Unless otherwise specified, the cycling, rate and self-discharge performance of Zn||RAP batteries in coin-type cells were once again assessed by GCD experiments with a Neware battery cycler at 25 °C. Zn metal was always used in excess, and the ratio of polymer cathode/Zn was 1/3 wt%. The cycling and rate performance of Zn||RAP batteries were also carried out by GCD experiments with a Biologic SP-150 at variable temperature in the range of +25 to –35 °C using Binder climatic chamber. As a commonly used procedure for polymer-based organic batteries, the specific capacities, current rates, specific discharge energy/power were normalized with respect to the mass of polymer in the cathode. Specific discharge energy (Wh kg⁻¹) was calculated by integrating area under the galvanostatic specific capacity–voltage discharge profiles. Specific power (W kg⁻¹) was calculated by (specific discharge energy / discharge time) x 3600. Finally, electro-ionic response of the RAP/CNTs working electrode in different aqueous electrolytes was evaluated by EIS measurements in three-electrode configuration with Zn wire and Zn foil as the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. The EIS data were collected in the 0.01–10⁵ Hz frequency range using a sinusoidal signal with an amplitude of 10 mV ($V_{rms} \approx 7.07$ mV) at equilibrium discharge potential (1.15 V; ~50 % depth-of-discharge).

Supporting Information

Supporting table and figures are in Supporting Information.

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

- [1] Z. Yang, J. Zhang, M. C. W. Kintner-Meyer, X. Lu, D. Choi, J. P. Lemmon, J. Liu, *Chem. Rev.* **2011**, *111*, 3577.
- [2] D. Larcher, J.-M. Tarascon, *Nat. Chem.* **2015**, *7*, 19.
- [3] S. Chu, Y. Cui, N. Liu, *Nat. Mater.* **2017**, *16*, 16.
- [4] M. Li, J. Lu, Z. Chen, K. Amine, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 1800561.

- [5] K. Turcheniuk, D. Bondarev, V. Singhal, G. Yushin, *Nature* **2018**, 559, 467.
- [6] P. Canepa, G. Sai Gautam, D. C. Hannah, R. Malik, M. Liu, K. G. Gallagher, K. A. Persson, G. Ceder, *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, 117, 4287.
- [7] R. J. Gummow, G. Vamvounis, M. B. Kannan, Y. He, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, 30, 1801702.
- [8] J. Huang, Z. Guo, Y. Ma, D. Bin, Y. Wang, Y. Xia, *Small Methods* **2019**, 3, 1800272.
- [9] Y. Zhang, H. Geng, W. Wei, J. Ma, L. Chen, C. C. Li, *Energy Storage Mater.* **2019**, 20, 118.
- [10] V. Verma, S. Kumar, W. Manalastas, R. Satish, M. Srinivasan, *Adv. Sustain. Syst.* **2019**, 3, 1970004.
- [11] G. A. Elia, K. Marquardt, K. Hoepfner, S. Fantini, R. Lin, E. Knipping, W. Peters, J.-F. Drillet, S. Passerini, R. Hahn, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, 28, 7564.
- [12] M. Song, H. Tan, D. Chao, H. J. Fan, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, 28, 1802564.
- [13] A. Konarov, N. Voronina, J. H. Jo, Z. Bakenov, Y.-K. Sun, S.-T. Myung, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, 3, 2620.
- [14] J. Ming, J. Guo, C. Xia, W. Wang, H. N. Alshareef, *Mater. Sci. Eng. R Reports* **2019**, 135, 58.
- [15] X. Zeng, J. Hao, Z. Wang, J. Mao, Z. Guo, *Energy Storage Mater.* **2019**, 20, 410.
- [16] H. Li, L. Ma, C. Han, Z. Wang, Z. Liu, Z. Tang, C. Zhi, *Nano Energy* **2019**, 62, 550.
- [17] L. Ma, M. A. Schroeder, O. Borodin, T. P. Pollard, M. S. Ding, C. Wang, K. Xu, *Nat. Energy* **2020**, 5, 743.
- [18] G. Fang, J. Zhou, A. Pan, S. Liang, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, 3, 2480.
- [19] L. Chen, Q. An, L. Mai, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, 6, 1900387.

- [20] S. Muench, A. Wild, C. Friebe, B. Häupler, T. Janoschka, U. S. Schubert, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 9438.
- [21] J. Kim, J. H. Kim, K. Ariga, *Joule* **2017**, *1*, 739.
- [22] S. Lee, G. Kwon, K. Ku, K. Yoon, S.-K. Jung, H.-D. Lim, K. Kang, *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 1704682.
- [23] K. Amin, L. Mao, Z. Wei, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2019**, *40*, 1800565.
- [24] P. Poizot, J. Gaubicher, S. Renault, L. Dubois, Y. Liang, Y. Yao, *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, acs.chemrev.9b00482.
- [25] Y. Chen, S. Zhuo, Z. Li, C. Wang, *EnergyChem* **2020**, 100030.
- [26] Y. Lu, J. Chen, *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2020**, *4*, 127.
- [27] J. Xie, Q. Zhang, *Small* **2019**, *15*, 1805061.
- [28] B. T. McAllister, L. T. Kyne, T. B. Schon, D. S. Seferos, *Joule* **2019**, *3*, 620.
- [29] J. Cui, Z. Guo, J. Yi, X. Liu, K. Wu, P. Liang, Q. Li, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, Y. Xia, J. Zhang, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, *13*, 2160.
- [30] S. Xu, M. Sun, Q. Wang, C. Wang, *J. Semicond.* **2020**, *41*, 091704.
- [31] N. Patil, A. Mavrandonakis, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, J. Palma, R. Marcilla, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *2*, 3035.
- [32] N. Patil, A. Mavrandonakis, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, N. Casado, D. Mecerreyes, J. Palma, R. Marcilla, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2021**, *9*, 505.
- [33] T. Nokami, T. Matsuo, Y. Inatomi, N. Hojo, T. Tsukagoshi, H. Yoshizawa, A. Shimizu, H. Kuramoto, K. Komae, H. Tsuyama, J. Yoshida, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 19694.

- [34] N. Patil, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2018**, *82*, 34.
- [35] M. Krogsgaard, V. Nue, H. Birkedal, *Chem. - A Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 844.
- [36] N. Zhang, F. Cheng, Y. Liu, Q. Zhao, K. Lei, C. Chen, X. Liu, J. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 12894.
- [37] F. Wang, O. Borodin, T. Gao, X. Fan, W. Sun, F. Han, A. Faraone, J. A. Dura, K. Xu, C. Wang, *Nat. Mater.* **2018**, *17*, 543.
- [38] J. Zhao, J. Zhang, W. Yang, B. Chen, Z. Zhao, H. Qiu, S. Dong, X. Zhou, G. Cui, L. Chen, *Nano Energy* **2019**, *57*, 625.
- [39] F. Wan, Y. Zhang, L. Zhang, D. Liu, C. Wang, L. Song, Z. Niu, J. Chen, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 7062.
- [40] Z. Liu, Q. Yang, D. Wang, G. Liang, Y. Zhu, F. Mo, Z. Huang, X. Li, L. Ma, T. Tang, Z. Lu, C. Zhi, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *9*, 1902473.
- [41] Z. Peng, Q. Wei, S. Tan, P. He, W. Luo, Q. An, L. Mai, *Chem. Commun.* **2018**, *54*, 4041.
- [42] Y. Jin, L. Zou, L. Liu, M. H. Engelhard, R. L. Patel, Z. Nie, K. S. Han, Y. Shao, C. Wang, J. Zhu, H. Pan, J. Liu, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 1900567.
- [43] L. Ma, N. Li, C. Long, B. Dong, D. Fang, Z. Liu, Y. Zhao, X. Li, J. Fan, S. Chen, S. Zhang, C. Zhi, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *29*, 1906142.
- [44] L. Cao, D. Li, T. Deng, Q. Li, C. Wang, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 19292.
- [45] B. Lan, C. Tang, L. Chen, W. Zhang, W. Tang, C. Zuo, X. Fu, S. Dong, Q. An, P. Luo, *J. Alloys Compd.* **2020**, *818*, 153372.
- [46] S. Wu, Y. Chen, T. Jiao, J. Zhou, J. Cheng, B. Liu, S. Yang, K. Zhang, W. Zhang, *Adv. Energy*

Mater. **2019**, *9*, 1902915.

- [47] L. Wang, K.-W. Huang, J. Chen, J. Zheng, *Sci. Adv.* **2019**, *5*, eaax4279.
- [48] B. W. Olbasa, F. W. Fenta, S.-F. Chiu, M.-C. Tsai, C.-J. Huang, B. A. Jote, T. T. Beyene, Y.-F. Liao, C.-H. Wang, W.-N. Su, H. Dai, B. J. Hwang, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 4499.
- [49] Z. Zhao, J. Zhao, Z. Hu, J. Li, J. Li, Y. Zhang, C. Wang, G. Cui, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2019**, *12*, 1938.
- [50] B. W. Olbasa, F. W. Fenta, S.-F. Chiu, M.-C. Tsai, C.-J. Huang, B. A. Jote, T. T. Beyene, Y.-F. Liao, C.-H. Wang, W.-N. Su, H. Dai, B. J. Hwang, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *3*, 4499.
- [51] B. D. Adams, J. Zheng, X. Ren, W. Xu, J.-G. Zhang, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, *8*, 1702097.
- [52] L. Cao, D. Li, T. Pollard, T. Deng, B. Zhang, C. Yang, L. Chen, J. Vatamanu, E. Hu, M. J. Hourwitz, L. Ma, M. Ding, Q. Li, S. Hou, K. Gaskell, J. T. Fourkas, X. Yang, K. Xu, O. Borodin, C. Wang, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2021**, DOI 10.1038/s41565-021-00905-4.
- [53] H. Qiu, X. Du, J. Zhao, Y. Wang, J. Ju, Z. Chen, Z. Hu, D. Yan, X. Zhou, G. Cui, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 5374.
- [54] J. Han, A. Mariani, H. Zhang, M. Zarrabeitia, X. Gao, D. V. Carvalho, A. Varzi, S. Passerini, *Energy Storage Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 196.
- [55] L. Jiang, L. Liu, J. Yue, Q. Zhang, A. Zhou, O. Borodin, L. Suo, H. Li, L. Chen, K. Xu, Y. Hu, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 1904427.
- [56] M. R. Lukatskaya, J. I. Feldblyum, D. G. Mackanic, F. Lissel, D. L. Michels, Y. Cui, Z. Bao, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2018**, *11*, 2876.
- [57] V. Vchirawongkwin, B. M. Rode, I. Persson, *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2007**, *111*, 4150.

- [58] N. Zhang, F. Cheng, J. Liu, L. Wang, X. Long, X. Liu, F. Li, J. Chen, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 405.
- [59] X. Yue, H. Liu, P. Liu, *Chem. Commun.* **2019**, *55*, 1647.
- [60] N. Patil, D. Cordella, A. Aqil, A. Debuigne, S. Admassie, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49*, 7676.
- [61] Z. Guo, Y. Ma, X. Dong, J. Huang, Y. Wang, Y. Xia, *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 11737.
- [62] S. Zhang, W. Zhao, H. Li, Q. Xu, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, *13*, 188.
- [63] Q. Zhao, W. Huang, Z. Luo, L. Liu, Y. Lu, Y. Li, L. Li, J. Hu, H. Ma, J. Chen, *Sci. Adv.* **2018**, *4*, eaao1761.
- [64] E. Laviron, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.* **1979**, *101*, 19.
- [65] N. Patil, A. Aqil, F. Ouhib, S. Admassie, O. Inganäs, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 1703373.
- [66] N. Patil, M. Aqil, A. Aqil, F. Ouhib, R. Marcilla, A. Minoia, R. Lazzaroni, C. Jérôme, C. Detrembleur, *Chem. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 5831.
- [67] D. Kundu, P. Oberholzer, C. Glaros, A. Bouzid, E. Tervoort, A. Pasquarello, M. Niederberger, *Chem. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 3874.
- [68] H. Glatz, E. Lizundia, F. Pacifico, D. Kundu, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *2*, 1288.
- [69] K. W. Nam, H. Kim, Y. Beldjoudi, T. Kwon, D. J. Kim, J. F. Stoddart, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 2541.
- [70] Y. Wang, C. Wang, Z. Ni, Y. Gu, B. Wang, Z. Guo, Z. Wang, D. Bin, J. Ma, Y. Wang, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 2000338.

- [71] H. Zhang, Y. Fang, F. Yang, X. Liu, X. Lu, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2020**, *13*, 2515.
- [72] Q. Wang, X. Xu, G. Yang, Y. Liu, X. Yao, *Chem. Commun.* **2020**, *56*, 11859.
- [73] Q. Wang, Y. Liu, P. Chen, *J. Power Sources* **2020**, *468*, 228401.
- [74] G. Dawut, Y. Lu, L. Miao, J. Chen, *Inorg. Chem. Front.* **2018**, *5*, 1391.
- [75] K. W. Nam, S. S. Park, R. dos Reis, V. P. Dravid, H. Kim, C. A. Mirkin, J. F. Stoddart, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 4948.
- [76] B. Häupler, C. Rössel, A. M. Schwenke, J. Winsberg, D. Schmidt, A. Wild, U. S. Schubert, *NPG Asia Mater.* **2016**, *8*, e283.
- [77] P. Li, Z. Fang, Y. Zhang, C. Mo, X. Hu, J. Jian, S. Wang, D. Yu, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7*, 17292.
- [78] Y. Luo, F. Zheng, L. Liu, K. Lei, X. Hou, G. Xu, H. Meng, J. Shi, F. Li, *ChemSusChem* **2020**, *13*, 2239.
- [79] M. Yu, N. Chandrasekhar, R. K. M. Raghupathy, K. H. Ly, H. Zhang, E. Dmitrieva, C. Liang, X. Lu, T. D. Kühne, H. Mirhosseini, I. M. Weidinger, X. Feng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 19570.
- [80] C. Wang, T. He, J. Cheng, Q. Guan, B. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 2004430.
- [81] A. Khayum M, M. Ghosh, V. Vijayakumar, A. Halder, M. Nurhuda, S. Kumar, M. Addicoat, S. Kurungot, R. Banerjee, *Chem. Sci.* **2019**, *10*, 8889.
- [82] L. Chen, Z. Yang, Y. Huang, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 13032.
- [83] T. Wei, Q. Li, G. Yang, C. Wang, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2018**, *6*, 8006.
- [84] V. Soundharrajan, B. Sambandam, S. Kim, M. H. Alfaruqi, D. Y. Putro, J. Jo, S. Kim, V.

Mathew, Y. K. Sun, J. Kim, *Nano Lett.* **2018**, *18*, 2402.

- [85] B. Tang, J. Zhou, G. Fang, F. Liu, C. Zhu, C. Wang, A. Pan, S. Liang, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7*, 940.
- [86] W. Zhou, J. Chen, M. Chen, A. Wang, A. Huang, X. Xu, J. Xu, C.-P. Wong, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, *8*, 8397.
- [87] H. Wang, J. Liu, J. Wang, M. Hu, Y. Feng, P. Wang, Y. Wang, N. Nie, J. Zhang, H. Chen, Q. Yuan, J. Wu, Y. Huang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 49.
- [88] M. Chen, W. Zhou, A. Wang, A. Huang, J. Chen, J. Xu, C.-P. Wong, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2020**, *8*, 6828.
- [89] Q. Zhang, Y. Ma, Y. Lu, L. Li, F. Wan, K. Zhang, J. Chen, *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11*, 4463.
- [90] S.-L. Chou, Y. Pan, J.-Z. Wang, H.-K. Liu, S.-X. Dou, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2014**, *16*, 20347.

ToC entries

An Ultrahigh Performance Zinc-Organic Battery Using Poly(catechol) Cathode in Zn(TFSI)₂ Based Concentrated Aqueous Electrolytes

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ToC text:

Ultrahigh performance Zn–polymer aqueous battery based on abundant Zn metal anode, novel 4 m Zn(TFSI)₂-H₂O electrolyte and bioinspired poly(catechol) cathode is reported. This Zn||P(4VC₈₆-stat-SS₁₄) cell delivered the highest specific energy/power of ~352 Wh kg_{polymer}⁻¹/~150 kW kg_{polymer}⁻¹, together with remarkable cycling stability (83% capacity retention over 48000 cycles at 30C) and low temperature operativity (178 mAh g⁻¹ at –35 °C).

ToC keyword: Zinc-Organic Batteries

ToC figure:

